

RESEARCH ARTICLE | JANUARY 29 2024

Effect of temperature on magnetic properties and magnetoimpedance effect of Co-rich glass-coated microwires

Special Collection: [68th Annual Conference on Magnetism and Magnetic Materials](#)

P. Corte-Leon

AIP Advances 14, 015248 (2024)
<https://doi.org/10.1063/9.0000666>

CrossMark

Biomicrofluidics
Special Topic:
Microfluidic Biosensors
Submit Today

Effect of temperature on magnetic properties and magnetoimpedance effect of Co-rich glass-coated microwires

Cite as: AIP Advances 14, 015248 (2024); doi: 10.1063/9.0000666
Submitted: 30 September 2023 • Accepted: 15 November 2023 •
Published Online: 29 January 2024

View Online

Export Citation

CrossMark

P. Corte-Leon,^{1,2,3,a)} I. Skorvanek,⁴ F. Andrejka,⁴ M. Jakubcin,⁴ V. Zhukova,^{1,2}
and A. Zhukov^{1,2,3,5,a)}

AFFILIATIONS

¹ Department of Polymers and Advanced Materials: Physics, Chemistry and Technology, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Basque Country, UPV/EHU, 20018 San Sebastian, Spain

² Department of Applied Physics I, Escuela de Ingeniería de Gipuzkoa EIG, University of Basque Country, UPV/EHU, Plaza Europa 1, 20018 San Sebastian, Spain

³ EHU Quantum Center, University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, San Sebastian, Spain

⁴ Institute of Experimental Physics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Kosice, Slovakia

⁵ IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48011 Bilbao, Spain

Note: This paper was presented at the 68th Annual Conference on Magnetism and Magnetic Materials.

a) Authors to whom correspondence should be addressed: paula.corte@ehu.es and arkadi.joukov@ehu.es,
Tel.: 34943018611, Fax: 34-943017130

ABSTRACT

We studied the effect of heating on the magnetic properties and giant magnetoimpedance (GMI), effect of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires with vanishing magnetostriction. We observed, that upon heating the hysteresis loop changed its shape from inclined to rectangular. These changes in hysteresis loop shape correlate with modification of magnetic field dependencies of GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, from double-peak to single-peak and with change in value of maximum GMI ratio. The origin of the observed changes in the hysteresis loop and the GMI effect is discussed in terms of the Hopkinson effect, internal stresses relaxation upon heating, and the temperature dependencies of internal stresses and the magnetostriction coefficient.

© 2024 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). <https://doi.org/10.1063/9.0000666>

I. INTRODUCTION

Amorphous magnetic materials are generally considered to be among the most attractive magnetic materials due to unusual combination of their excellent magnetic and mechanical properties and relatively simple and fast fabrication and post-processing.^{1–7}

Among unusual magnetic properties with high technological interest reported for amorphous materials are magnetic bistability^{5,8,9} and/or giant magnetoimpedance (GMI), effect.^{3,5,10} Although both GMI effect and magnetic bistability can be observed in amorphous ribbons,^{3,8} spontaneous magnetic bistability and the highest GMI effect are usually associated with amorphous magnetic wires.^{3,5,9,10} Therefore, studies of

amorphous wires are in the focus of intensive studies since the '70s.^{3,5,9,10}

Emerging applications of amorphous materials stimulated development of new technologies for fabrication of amorphous wires with reduced dimensions, enhanced corrosion resistance and biocompatibility.^{5,6,11,12} Therefore, much attention is paid to the development of technologies suitable for fabrication of biocompatible amorphous wires with reduced dimensionality.^{5,6,11–13} So-called Taylor–Ulitsky fabrication method allows to prepare amorphous microwires with the most extended metallic nucleus diameters range (from 0.2 to 100 μm),^{14,15} covered with thin, insulating, biocompatible and flexible glass-coating. Such glass-coated microwires prepared and post-processed at appropriate conditions can present

excellent magnetic softness, among the highest GMI ratios or magnetic bistability.^{5,16,17} Such features of glass-coated microwires make them suitable for novel technological applications.^{6,18,19} Among the most prospective applications of glass-coated microwires is the development of smart composites with magnetic microwire inclusions allowing external stimuli (magnetic field, applied stress or temperature) monitoring.^{20–24}

The concept of tunable composites with magnetic microwire inclusions is based on the theoretically predicted and experimentally demonstrated dependence of the effective permittivity of composites containing magnetically soft wire inclusions on the external stimuli such as magnetic field, stress or temperature.^{20,21,25} Use of magnetically soft microwires embedded into such composites is based on sensitivity of high-frequency impedance to applied stress, temperature and magnetic field, which can be remotely monitored using free space microwave spectroscopy.^{20,21,25} Potential impact of such tunable composites in various industries, such as aircraft or automobile industries or civil engineering is extremely relevant. However, influence of magnetic field or applied stress on GMI effect at elevated (up to GHz) frequencies and on effective permittivity of composites with magnetic wire inclusions is reported in several publications,^{20–26} only a few papers report on temperature dependence of GMI effect.^{27,28} Additionally, effect of temperature on GMI effect has been studied either in rather limited temperature range or in different type of magnetic wires.^{27,28}

Quite recently, we reported on substantial temperature dependence of magnetic properties and GMI effect in Fe-rich glass-coated microwires.²⁹ A remarkable GMI effect improvement and modification of hysteresis loops upon heating up to 300 °C of FeSiBC microwires was observed.²⁹

In this paper we report our most last experimental results on the effect of heating on the GMI effect and hysteresis loops of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires with nearly-zero magnetostriction.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

We studied amorphous $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires with metallic nucleus diameter $d = 22.8 \mu\text{m}$ and total diameter $D = 23.2 \mu\text{m}$, prepared by modified Taylor–Ulitsky fabrication technique.

The fabrication method (commonly called the Taylor–Ulitsky method) essentially consists of melting a metal ingot inside a Duran-type glass tube using a high-frequency inductor, drawing the molten metallic alloy surrounded by a softened glass capillary, and winding the glass-coated microwires onto a rotating reel.^{11,30,31} Such fabrication method is known since the '60s,^{32,33} however was substantially modified during last 3 decades.^{30,31}

The magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , (-0.3×10^{-6}) of studied microwire has been measured previously using the small angle magnetization rotation (SAMR) method.³³ The amorphous structure of studied samples has been previously confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) data.³⁴

Hysteresis loops of studied $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwire were measured using the vibration sample magnetometer (VSM) MicroSense EV9 and the fluxmetric method.^{29,35} The measurements were performed from room temperature up to 300 °C, as previously described elsewhere.²⁹

To assess the GMI effect, the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, was used, defined as^{11–13}

$$\Delta Z/Z = [Z(H) - Z(H_{\max})]/Z(H_{\max}) \quad (1)$$

where Z is the microwire impedance, H and H_{\max} are the applied DC magnetic field and the maximum applied magnetic field, respectively.

A specially developed experimental setup allowed GMI effect measurements in a temperature, T , range from room temperature to 300 °C at frequencies up to 110 MHz.³⁶

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Low-field hysteresis loop of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwires measured at room temperature is shown in Fig. 1. As can be seen from Fig. 1, studied microwire presents excellent magnetic softness with coercivity, H_c , about 4 A/m and magnetic anisotropy field, H_k , about 180 A/m.

However, as shown in Fig. 2 upon heating the shape of the hysteresis loops changes from almost linear to nearly rectangular. The observed change in the hysteresis loop character is exactly the opposite of that recently reported for Fe-rich microwires in which the rectangular hysteresis loop turns into inclined one upon heating.²⁹

FIG. 1. Hysteresis loops of studied microwire at room temperature.

FIG. 2. Effect of heating on hysteresis loops of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwires.

On the other hand, transformation of linear hysteresis loop into rectangular has been previously observed in Co-rich microwires upon annealing.^{34,35} The origin of such hysteresis loops transformation from linear to rectangular is explained by change in the magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , value and sign.³⁴ Additionally, the relaxation of internal stresses should lead to a change in the domain structure related with an increase in the inner axially magnetized core volume and, hence, with a modification of the hysteresis loop.¹⁷

The observed change in hysteresis loops reflects a change in magnetic anisotropy of the studied microwires. As predicted, the $\Delta Z/Z$ magnitude and the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence are linked to the magnetic anisotropy of magnetic wires.³⁷ Therefore, one can expect change in $\Delta Z/Z$ -value and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies upon heating. Effect of temperature on $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies can be observed in Fig. 3, where $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at different temperatures, T , are provided.

As can be appreciated from Fig. 3, gradual change from double-peak to single peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence takes place upon heating.

Such change from double-peak to single peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence appears at $150 \leq T \leq 200$ °C: as can be seen from Fig. 4 at $T = 150$ °C double-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence is still observed for the whole frequency, f , range (at $10 \leq f \leq 100$ MHz) [see Fig. 4(b)]. While at $T \geq 200$ °C single-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence is observed for all f -values [see Fig. 4(c)].

As discussed elsewhere, the field of maximum, H_m , on $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies is associated with the magnetic anisotropy field at MHz frequencies.^{37,38} Therefore, observed change in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies upon heating correlates with the effect of heating on hysteresis loops provided in Fig. 2: change from weak transverse magnetic anisotropy to axial magnetic anisotropy.

We have tried to summarize observed dependence of GMI effect in Fig. 5, where we plot dependencies of maximum GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z_m$, and H_m versus temperature. Gradual decrease in H_m upon heating reflects change in both hysteresis loops and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies upon heating. On the other hand, a decrease in $\Delta Z/Z_m(T)$ is followed by an increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$. The decrease in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ must be associated with lower magnetic permeability of microwires with rectangular hysteresis loops. Such a decrease in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ upon annealing has been previously reported and explained by the transformation of linear hysteresis loop into rectangular upon annealing.³⁹

FIG. 3. Modification of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at 50 MHz upon heating of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwires.

FIG. 4. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwires measured at room temperature (a), at 150 °C (b) and at $T = 200$ °C (c).

Similarly to that discussed previously for Fe-rich microwires,²⁹ the increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ at $T \geq 200$ °C can be attributed to the Hopkinson effect.

The nature of the Hopkinson effect is usually associated to a faster decrease in the magnetic anisotropy constant upon heating compared to a magnetization decrease.^{40,41} Accordingly, a magnetic permeability maximum can be observed at temperatures, slightly below the Curie temperature, T_c . Our previous experimental data revealed that T_c of studied sample is about 325 °C.³⁴ Therefore, such interpretation looks reasonable.

This assumption is indirectly confirmed by the evolution of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of studied Co-rich microwire upon heating above 200 °C and its comparison with $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence measured at room temperature after heating to 300 °C and consequently cooled to room temperature of studied Co-rich microwire

FIG. 5. $\Delta Z/Z_m(T)$ and $H_m(T)$ dependencies evaluated from $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies.

[see Fig. 6(a)]. Single peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed at $T \geq 200^\circ\text{C}$ [see Fig. 6(a)]. As can be observed from Fig. 6(a), the $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values gradually increase when heating to 300°C . The lowest $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are observed after cooling from 300°C to room temperature. Accordingly, when heated to 300°C , an increase in the $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values is observed, despite the rectangular hysteresis loops character. Therefore, in our opinion, the observed increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ at 300°C can be associated with the Hopkinson effect. The relatively moderate increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ at 300°C compared to Fe-rich

FIG. 6. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at $f = 110\text{ MHz}$ at $200, 250, 300^\circ\text{C}$ and after cooling to room temperature (a) and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies in as-prepared samples and after cooling from 300°C (b).

microwires must be attributed to the transformation of an inclined hysteresis loop into rectangular one upon heating, which is usually not favorable for GMI effect optimization.

On the other hand, relaxation of internal stresses upon heating must affect the magnetoelastic anisotropy of studied microwires. As discussed elsewhere,^{17,43} circumferential magnetic anisotropy in Co-rich wires with low and negative magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , is interpreted considering the features of internal stresses arising during the fabrication process. In the case of glass-coated microwires most of internal stresses are originated by a simultaneous rapid quenching of a metallic nucleus inside the glass-coating with rather different thermal expansion coefficients.^{17,30,42} The largest internal stresses component is of the axial origin within the most portion of the metallic nucleus.^{17,30,42} Accordingly, change in the magnetostriction coefficient sign upon heating or even change in the internal stresses (with mostly axial orientation) must affect the magnetic anisotropy and hence $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of studied Co-rich microwire.

This assumption is confirmed by irreversible change in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies and in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values of studied Co-rich microwire after heating to 300°C followed by its cooling to room temperature [see Fig. 6(b)].

Accordingly, the possible origins of observed temperature dependences are either the Hopkinson effect, change of the internal stresses and temperature dependence of the magnetostriction coefficient.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have observed substantial influence of heating on the magnetic properties and giant magnetoimpedance, GMI, effect of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires with vanishing magnetostriction. The hysteresis loop changed its shape from inclined to rectangular upon heating. Observed changes in hysteresis loops correlate with the modification of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies from double-peak to single-peak and with change in value of maximum GMI ratio.

The origin of the observed influence of heating on hysteresis loops, $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies and GMI ratio values is discussed, considering the contributions from the Hopkinson effect, the temperature dependencies of the magnetostriction coefficient and the internal stresses as well as the internal stresses relaxation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by EU under “INFINITE” (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01-06) project, by the Spanish MICIN under PID2022-141373NB-I00, by the Government of the Basque Country under PUE_2021_1_0009, Elkartek (MINERVA, MAGAF and ZE-KONP) projects and under the scheme of “Ayuda a Grupos Consolidados” (Ref. No. IT1670-22). The authors thank for technical and human support provided by SGiker of UPV/EHU (Medidas Magnéticas Gipuzkoa) and European funding (ERDF and ESF). The group at the Institute of Experimental Physics SAS acknowledges support of the projects VEGA 2/0148/23 and APVV-19-0369. We wish to thank the administration of the University of the Basque Country, which not only provides very limited funding, but even appropriates the resources received by the research group from

private companies for the research activities of the group. Such interference helps keep us on our toes.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

P. Corte-Leon: Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **I. Skorvanek:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **F. Andrejka:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal). **M. Jakubcin:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal). **V. Zhukova:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal). **A. Zhukov:** Conceptualization (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- J. Lenz and S. Edelstein, *IEEE Sens. J.* **6**, 631 (2006).
- F. Fiorillo, G. Bertotti, C. Appino, and M. Pasquale, “Soft magnetic materials,” in *Wiley Encyclopedia of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, edited by J. Webster (John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Torino, Italy, 1999), p. 42.
- M. Knobel, M. Vazquez, and L. Kraus, *Handbook Magn. Mater.* **15**, 497 (2003).
- G. Herzer, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **254–255**, 598 (2003).
- A. Zhukov, M. Ipatov, P. Corte-León, L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, J. M. Blanco, and V. Zhukova, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **498**, 166180 (2020).
- D. Kozejova, L. Fecova, P. Klein, R. Sabol, R. Hudak, I. Sulla, D. Mudronova, J. Galik, and R. Varga, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **470**, 2 (2019).
- T. Goto, M. Nagano, and N. Wehara, *Trans. JIM* **18**, 759 (1977).
- A. P. Zhukov, *Mater. Design* **5**, 299 (1993).
- K. Mohri, F. B. Humphrey, K. Kawashima, K. Kimura, and M. Mizutani, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **26**, 1789 (1990).
- K. Mohri, T. Uchiyama, L. P. Shen, C. M. Cai, and L. V. Panina, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **249**, 351 (2002).
- S. A. Baranov, V. S. Larin, and A. V. Torcunov, *Crystals* **7**, 136 (2017).
- P. Rudkowski, G. Rudkowska, and J. O. Strom-Olsen, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* **133**, 158–161 (1991).
- O. Mitxelena-Iribarren, J. Campisi, I. Martínez de Apellániz, S. Lizarbe-Sancha, S. Arana, V. Zhukova, M. Mujika, and A. Zhukov, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* **106**, 110261 (2020).
- H. Chiriac, N. Lupu, G. Stoian, G. Ababei, S. Corodeanu, and T.-A. Óvári, *Crystals* **7**, 48 (2017).
- P. Corte-Leon, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, J. González, M. Churyukanova, S. Taskaev, and A. Zhukov, *J. Alloys Compd.* **831**, 150992 (2020).
- M. Vázquez, A. Zhukov, P. Aragonese, J. Arcas, P. Marin, and A. Hernando, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **34**(3), 724 (1998).
- A. Zhukov, P. Corte-Leon, L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, A. Gonzalez, and V. Zhukova, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **55**, 253003 (2022).
- R. Sabol, P. Klein, T. Ryba, L. Hvizdos, R. Varga, M. Rovnak, I. Sulla, D. Mudronova, J. Galik, I. Polacek, J. Zivcak, and R. Hudak, *Acta Phys. Pol. A* **131**(4), 1150 (2017).
- V. Zhukova, P. Corte-Leon, J. M. Blanco, M. Ipatov, J. Gonzalez, and A. Zhukov, *Chemosensors* **9**, 100 (2021).
- D. P. Makhnovskiy and L. V. Panina, *J. Appl. Phys.* **93**, 4120 (2003).
- D. Makhnovskiy, A. Zhukov, V. Zhukova, and J. Gonzalez, *Advances in Science and Technology* **54**, 201 (2008).
- M. Ipatov, G. R. Aranda, V. Zhukova, L. V. Panina, J. González, and A. Zhukov, *Appl. Phys.* **103**(3), 693 (2011).
- A. Allue, P. Corte-León, K. Gondra, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, J. González, M. Churyukanova, S. Taskaev, and A. Zhukov, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* **120**, 12 (2019).
- A. Uddin, D. Estevez, and F. X. Qin, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* **153**, 106734 (2022).
- L. Panina, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, J. Gonzalez, and A. Zhukov, “Tuneable composites containing magnetic microwires,” in *Metal, Ceramic and Polymeric Composites for Various Uses*, Edited by J. Cuppoletti and J. Trdine (InTech - Open Access Publisher, 51000 Rijeka, Croatia, 2011), Vol. 9, Chap. II, pp. 431–460 ISBN: 978-953-307-353-8 (www.intechweb.org).
- L. V. Panina, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, and J. Gonzalez, *J. Appl. Phys.* **109**, 053901 (2011).
- L. V. Panina, A. Dzhumazoda, S. A. Evstigneeva, A. M. Adam, A. T. Morchenko, N. A. Yudanov, and V. G. Kostishyn, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **459**, 147 (2018).
- H. Chiriac, C. S. Marinescu, and T.-A. Óvári, *J. Alloys Compound.* **196–197**, 162 (1999).
- P. Corte-Leon, I. Skorvanek, F. Andrejka, V. Zhukova, J. M. Blanco, M. Ipatov, and A. Zhukov, *J. Alloys Compound.* **946**, 169419 (2023).
- T.-A. Óvári, N. Lupu, and H. Chiriac, *Rapidly Solidified Magnetic Nanowires and Submicron Wires in Advanced Magnetic Materials* (InTech Open Access Publisher, Rijeka, Croatia, 2012), pp. 1–32.
- V. Zhukova, J. M. Blanco, M. Ipatov, J. Gonzalez, M. Churyukanova, and A. Zhukov, *Scr. Mater.* **142**, 10 (2018).
- A. V. Ulitovskiy, I. M. Maianski, and A. I. Avramenco, *Bulletin*, U.S.S.R. patent No. 128427 (1960), Vol. 10, p. 14.
- L. Kraus, J. Schneider, and H. Wiesner, *Czech. J. Phys.* **26**, 601 (1976).
- L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, P. Corte-León, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, M. Churyukanova, S. Taskaev, and A. Zhukov, *J. Alloys Compd.* **830**, 154576 (2020).
- L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, P. Corte-Leon, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, J. Gonzalez, and A. Zhukov, *Sensors* **20**, 1558 (2020).
- F. Andrejka, “Influence of thermal treatment in external magnetic field on microstructure and magnetic properties of selected rapidly quenched alloys,” Doctoral Dissertation (Technical University, Kosice, Slovakia, 2018).
- N. A. Usov, A. S. Antonov, and A. Lagar'kov, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **185**, 159 (1998).
- L. V. Panina, K. Mohri, T. Uchiyama *et al.*, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **31**(2), 1249 (1995).
- A. Zhukov, A. Talaat, M. Churyukanova, S. Kaloshkin, V. Semenkova, M. Ipatov, J. M. Blanco, and V. Zhukova, *J. Alloys Compd.* **664**, 235 (2016).
- K. He, H. Xu, Z. Wang, and L. Cheng, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* **16**, 145 (2000).
- V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, A. Talaat, and A. Zhukov, *Phys. Status Solidi C* **11**(5–6), 1130 (2014).
- A. V. Torcunov, S. A. Baranov, and V. S. Larin, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **196–197**, 835 (1999).
- J. N. Nderu, M. Takajo, J. Yamasaki, and F. B. Humphrey, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **34**(4), 1312 (1998).